

Indonesian Beauty Vloggers' Use of English and Its Influence towards its Viewers' Purchase Intention

Hairus Salikin¹, Agung Tri Wahyuningsih², Sofya Poerwanta³

^{1,2,3} English Department, Faculty of Humanities, Jember University

ABSTRACT: Vlog or video blog is now booming along with the existence of YouTube. In Indonesia, YouTube is a third rank of most visiting website in Indonesia (<https://www.alexacom/topsites/countries/ID>). This social media platform is advantageously employed to filming the actions which are easily accessed by public and it offers free video hosting which means vloggers may post unlimited videos without paying web hosting fees. Some vloggers perform videos for fun while others display for revenue generating through advertisements. Westenberg (cited in Subramani & Rajagopalan, 2003:302) mentions that YouTubers are influential in encouraging trial and adoption of new products and services. In line with Westenberg's idea, Edward (2011:11) adds that "interactive advertising can be targeted in more sophisticated ways than print ads, we must recognize that power of social media as means of persuasion is far beyond that of another vehicle in which to serve advertising." These two complementary propositions interest the researchers to conduct a deeper investigation about some vlogs on YouTube with the other variable of parameter, English use. The use of English gives efficacious consequence on advertisements. Biswal (2009:32) strongly mentioned that the use of two languages attracts consumers. Thus, capturing the four Indonesian beauty vloggers, assorted by the two who frequently insert some English codes and the other two who rarely interpolate them, as the object of research, this current investigation examines its use and influence towards viewers' purchase intention. Questionnaire as helpful instrument is going to be delivered to viewers to see their purchase intention based on the indicators proposed by Schiffman and Kanuk (2009). The result shows that English codes do not significantly influence the viewers' purchase intention. Viewers prefer beauty vlogs which are variously performed (not monotonous), humorously presented, and politely language-used. Besides, the content of the vlogs should be novel and honest.

KEYWORDS: Beauty vlogger, English use, Viewers' purchase intention

INTRODUCTION

Vlog which stands for video blog or video log puts trough video footage. A vlogger may post the video footage on any platform, either their own website or video sharing sites, like YouTube. Smith (2017) observed that most vloggers culled YouTube among some sites to publish their vlogs because of its popularity. In the site vloggingpro (2018), the popularity of vlogs published in YouTube has risen exponentially in the last few years.

Source = <https://vloggingpro.com/what-is-a-vlog-and-what-does-vlogging-mean/>

Many believe that the upgrading popularity is effectuated by the growth of technology that has produced massive equipment with affordable price and easily accessed by people around the globe. People who have a video-capable camera and an internet

connection can create a vlog and publish it online. Thus, it facilitates them to become vloggers facilely. Many vloggers, even, have opted it for sustainable careers and some of them have made money.

A weighty finding of a research conducted by Rahmawan et al (2017) shows that vlog has advanced a peculiar entity of business in the advertisement and digital media industry. A vlogger, since then, can be seen as micro-celebrity and online influencer who impress viewers, especially the youth. An interview to an agent of promotion reveals that vlog willy-nilly has been a promotion media when they want to forward certainly specific product to the youth. Seen as micro celebrity and online influencer, a vlogger becomes a persona who fascinates viewers. Viewers with enthusiasm alter them to be fans of vloggers. They expose their likeness by selecting feature “like” (a thumb up) and “subscribe” to follow their succeeding vlogs. The higher amount of the likeness and subscribers, the more influential the vlog is.

Raun (2018) assuredly agitates the role of social media platforms towards the new sub cultural form of micro-celebrity. Displaying the difference between micro-celebrity and mainstream celebrity in terms of utilizing YouTube as one of social media platforms, micro-celebrities are more responsive to viewers who require direct and fast response. This effort helps to narrow the gap between them and viewers. Narrowing the gap gives corollary of being close or intimate. Further, closeness or intimacy turns into a strategy to appeal the viewers. Raun denominates it as a genre at play that the vlogger used to create vlogs. He also appoints it as the capital for the vlogger to perform. The vlogger whom he investigated, Julie Van Vu is the Canadian vlogger with the nature of beauty vlogging. Her trans status might bring about controversial notion among her trans audience concerning with her explicit commercialization of self and content. Regardless of this, her vlog performance within the genre of beauty vlogging capitalizing intimacy might be particularly inspirational, as her way to beautify her female identity is hard to evidence.

Resembling study dealing with the identical genre of vlogging is carried on by Widodo and Mawardi (2017). They conducted a research on the influence of beauty vlogger toward source characteristics and its impact on purchase intention. Electing one beauty vlogger to study, Widodo and Mawardi rummage that the vlogger as the electronic word of mouth (eWom) is significantly influential apropos the source characteristics with the number of correlation coefficient 43,6%. Further, the source characteristics comprising *source credibility*, *source attractiveness*, and *source power* are powerfully suggestive related to purchase intention with correlation coefficient 53%. Finally, catenating two variables, the vlogger as eWom and purchase intention, appears essentially the number of correlation coefficient 53% which denotes the necessarily connected variables. Closing out their thorough examination on the three variables, they espy the strongly chained connection among vlogger as eWom, source characteristics and purchase intention.

Herlinda (2018) apprised marketers to avail YouTube as reciprocally active media platform to promote product. She shared some substantial tips in searching commercial trend on YouTube so that marketers can take the advantage of it. Discovering what is the most frequently searched, shared, and commented on YouTube is primarily recommended. Then, conforming the more forceful vloggers’ action, looking at the coequal vlogs and tag, and complying with their ingenious approach in producing vlogs are the ensuing things that should be paid attention to. Additionally, trolling trending topics that are widely spread among society is the other way to complete the tips. The last point to convince is the language use. The facticity and appropriateness of the language power the alluring vlogs. When the language used is convincing, viewers will be captivated.

The following profound examination on the influence of YouTubers on teenagers was executed by Westenberg (2016). To meet the goals of the study, four Netherland YouTubers and sixteen young viewers were interviewed. The foremost finding discloses that YouTube is being part of the teenagers’ daily life. They spend about 11 hours to watch YouTube in a week. Secondly, the youth feel more attracted to micro-celebrity or YouTubers than traditional TV celebrities. They imitate things YouTubers do, such as wearing the same clothes and make up, using the same humor and fillers, and in some cases, they copy bad behaviour and make mischief. The following finding results that YouTubers give huge influence toward teenagers’ buying behaviour. They think that YouTubers are honest about the products promoted and want to buy them as YouTubers have. The bottommost result shows that young viewers are unconsciously subject to the YouTubers. They have bought products recommended by YouTubers and have copied their behaviour.

Capturing the sights of the above prior investigations, some points are noted as the significant particulars for this current research. Most vlogs are publicly posted on YouTube, therefore it is supposed to use both, people who created a vlog, vloggers and YouTubers interchangeably. Vloggers or YouTubers are mainly considered as micro-celebrity and online influencer. Some utilize vlogs for promotion media as some vlogs are very forceful to grasp viewers’ attention, subsuming purchase intention. Beauty vlogs are cherry-picked to be the samples of how vloggers are performing their self-commercialization. All the entire entities wrapped up,

this current research is strung to weave the new idea from those mentioned entities. As YouTube is functionally purposed for advertising either self-representation or product reviews, Edward's assertion "interactive advertising can be targeted in more sophisticated ways than print ads, we must recognize that power of social media as a means of persuasion is far beyond that of another vehicle in which to serve advertising" (2011) is fundamentally employed to meet the research goals, namely digging out the use of English codes in Indonesian beauty vloggers and its influence on viewers' purchase intention. Further, vlogs, aired on YouTube which may interpolate advertisement, own persuasive force. Joining English use, which may imply persuasive force, and purchase intention becomes the newly proposed investigation since English use is the novel variable used. Fortified by Biswal (2009:32) who asserted that the employment of two languages in advertisement charms the customers and Cerdeño (2010:1) who claimed that the desire of advertisers to mark their product by adding some foreign words denote positive values, this research turns to be more intriguing because the objects of this research are Indonesian vloggers whose native tongue is not English, but they use some English codes in their vlogs.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Purchase intention (Spears and Singh cited in Angkouw and Rumokoy, 2016: 1129) is delineated as a person's witting plan to make an effort to buy a product. According to Schiffman and Kanuk (cited in Chi et al, 2011: 2), purchase intention is possibly used to measure the possibility of consumers to buy a product. Thus, it is credited that the higher purchase intention, the larger purchase probability. Further, purchase intention indicates that consumers will follow their experience, preference and external environment to collect information, evaluate alternatives, and make purchase decision. Breaking down the ideas, Siswanto and Rumambi (2013: 4) abstracted Schiffman dan Kanuk into the ensuing points:

- a. Customer's interest to seek the information about a product
- b. Customer's consideration to buy the product
- c. Customer's desire to buy the product
- d. Customer's interest to try the product
- e. Customer's desire to own the product

Khairunnisak and Firman (2013) referring to Schiffman dan Kanuk outlined 5 indicators of purchase intention, namely =

- a. The interest of seeking information about a product
- b. The consideration of buying the product
- c. The interest of trying the product
- d. The desire to know the product
- e. The desire to buy the product

Farhani et al (2017:279) lying on Schiffman and Kanuk brought about the five indicators to reveal purchase intention. They are:

- a. Interested in searching information about a product.
- b. Considering to buy the product
- c. Interested in trying the product^[SEP]
- d. Willing to know the product^[SEP]
- e. Willing to have that product^[SEP]

Summing up all particulars of the above elaboration, this investigation is employing the moving steps of Farhani et al. Frankly, all scholars are possessing the same thought about the concept of purchase intention. Thus, picking up one – as it is done- in this research will not set them aside. Farhani at all are singled out since they elaborate those indicators in detail and imply ways of revealing purchase intention. The following chart is made as the adaptation of Farhani et al's indicators.

Chart 1. The Purchase Intention's indicators

METHOD

This research is designed qualitatively. All data taken are words, phrases, and clauses grasped from the transcription of 4 Indonesian beauty vloggers. Since they are grouped into two, those who frequently use English and those who do not, the data are detailed to see what English codes are existing there. To set about this investigation, settling criteria of the chosen beauty vloggers is determined, to tweet, reviewing products and performing make-up tutorial. Among 250 beauty vloggers (www.socialblade.com) who conform to the requirements, some are screened based on the number of subscriber and of the use of English codes. The last noted numbers of subscribers were on August 22nd, 2019 which then resulted 4 names of Indonesian beauty vloggers: Tasya Farasya (2.629.934 subscribers) and Rachel Goddard (1.930.162 subscribers) who hourly produce English; and Indira Kalistha (1.794.271 subscribers) and Ini Vindy (1.701.192 subscribers) who rarely mix English codes into their utterances. It is hardly detected that the beauty vloggers avoid English use since some beauty terms are commonly English. To encounter this matter, the numbers of English codes are counted to validate the data. The first two vloggers, Tasya Farasya inserts about 508 (11,9%) English codes among 4275 words she produced for the two vlogs chosen; and Rachel Goddard insinuates around 353 (14,7%) English codes among 2042 words she made on her 2 vlogs. The rest vloggers assorted as group of having less number of English codes are Indira Kalistha who has 169 (5,9%) English codes among 2822 words, and Ini Vindy who performs 321 (8,1%) English codes among 3935 words. Those

numbers of English codes are being the reason why their vlogs are then elected to be examined. The English codes selected cover all English words mentioning kinds of products, words explaining the products, and some other expressions. The name of brand and the products' label written in English are excluded from the selected English codes. Here are all beauty vlogs taken as the sources of data.

1. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1RrfsSnHkHc-rL5r8Qjh3IRzyurroM2Xe/view?usp=sharing>
2. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1y93nqZgsijUf1u0VHcHDyFkI1o3ADU7h/view?usp=sharing>
3. https://drive.google.com/file/d/1lQhwFrHe4-R_5jFIHqx4YRIUjnLs01uA/view?usp=sharing
4. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1blRIPyqhDIBm3IhLLj08Ub-9KKVtuIVL/view?usp=sharing>
5. https://drive.google.com/file/d/1e3CAMW63hSyasmGvSRD_GL-MAQNsooyp/view?usp=sharing
6. https://drive.google.com/file/d/1zj79fwIPQjnnkHtm8CZfAhjJEl3Jh_Q8/view?usp=sharing
7. https://drive.google.com/file/d/1fxO7G0Hu2WSrN39_vz-1vOueXwRpzpd-/view?usp=sharing
8. https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ZdnISMBMW8ax-ZWkhzZnHIG1-X_nEOI0/view?usp=sharing

The 8 shareable links are the vlogs of Tasya Farasya(1 and 2), Rachel Goddard (3 and 4), Indira Kalista (5 and 6) and Ini Vindy (7 and 8).

Further, the influence of English use on viewers' purchase intention is catechized. Discovering the solution of it, questionnaire is distributed to viewers via google form. Netting the viewers through Instagram and LINE platform media is initially done to selecting certain viewers who have ever watched the chosen beauty vloggers. Their confession bases the researchers to then hand the questionnaire. Those who have never watched one of the mentioned beauty vloggers are not passed the questionnaire. Lying on the reason of recognizing the object of research, all selected viewers are supposed to give their objective evaluation. The questionnaire is designed based on the derived proposition of Farhani et all which is derived from Schiffman and Kanuk (2009). Further, as it has been noted on the above section that this investigation is aimed at revealing the English use, the questions on the questionnaire are methodized to cover both variables, scilicet, English use and purchase intention. Here is the table comprising questions in the questionnaire and their purposes.

Table 1. Questions List and Their Purposes

No.	Questions	Purposes															
1.	<p><i>Apakah anda pernah menonton video Beauty Vlogger Indonesia berikut ini? (beri tanda “x” dalam tabel berikut).</i> – Have you ever watched the vlogs of the following beauty vloggers? (put “x” in the following table)</p> <table border="1" style="margin-left: 20px;"> <thead> <tr> <th>Nama</th> <th>Ya</th> <th>Tidak</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Tasya Farasya</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Rachel Goddard</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Indira Kalistha</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Ini Vindy</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Nama	Ya	Tidak	Tasya Farasya			Rachel Goddard			Indira Kalistha			Ini Vindy			This question is set to know which of the mentioned beauty vloggers seems to have more viewers.
Nama	Ya	Tidak															
Tasya Farasya																	
Rachel Goddard																	
Indira Kalistha																	
Ini Vindy																	
2.	<p><i>Berapa kali Anda menonton video Beaut y Vlogger Indonesia di atas? – How many times do you watch the vlogs of the above beauty vloggers?</i> a. 2-5 kali/minggu (2-5 times/week) b. 6-10 kali/minggu (6-10 times/week)</p>	This question is purposed to know viewers' interest toward their chosen beauty vloggers in number 1. The higher the number the more their interest is.															
3.	<p><i>Setelah menonton Beauty Vlogger Indonesia tersebut, apakah Anda tertarik untuk mencari informasi tentang produk makeup? – After watching beauty vloggers' vlogs, are you interested in seeking the information of the product?</i> a. Ya (Yes) b. Tidak (No)</p>	Questions number 3 – 7 (5 questions) are structured to reveal viewers' purchase intention – based on Schiffman and Kanuk's (2009) theory of consumer behaviour which are detailed by some scholars. These															

4.	<p><i>Apakah Anda mencoba mengumpulkan informasi lain tentang produk makeup? – Are you trying to collect more information about the product?</i></p> <p>a. <i>Ya</i> (Yes) b. <i>Tidak</i> (No)</p>	<p>questions are designed to fulfil the indicators of purchase intention as charted on the theoretical review.</p>
5.	<p><i>Apakah Anda merasa cocok dengan produk makeup? – Are you adapted to the use of the makeup product?</i></p> <p>a. <i>Ya</i> (Yes) b. <i>Tidak</i> (No)</p>	
6.	<p><i>Apakah Anda ingin mengetahui spesifikasi produk makeup? – Do you want to know the make-up product’s detailed precise presentation?</i></p> <p>a. <i>Ya</i> (Yes) b. <i>Tidak</i> (No)</p>	
7.	<p><i>Apakah Anda ingin membeli produk makeup? – Do you finally want to buy the product?</i></p> <p>a. <i>Ya</i> (Yes) b. <i>Tidak</i> (No)</p>	
8.	<p><i>Apakah Anda menyadari beauty vloggers Indonesia di atas menggunakan bahasa Inggris? – Are you aware of the use of English codes in those beauty vloggers’ vlogs?</i></p> <p>a. <i>Ya</i> (Yes) b. <i>Tidak</i> (No)</p>	<p>Questions number 8-10 are arranged to know the influence of English use toward viewers’ purchase intention.</p>
9.	<p><i>Apakah Anda tertarik menonton video beauty vloggers Indonesia di atas karena penggunaan bahasa Inggris?- Are you interested in watching beauty vloggers’ vlogs because of the English codes used?</i></p> <p>a. <i>Ya</i> (Yes) b. <i>Tidak</i> (No)</p>	
10.	<p><i>Apakah Anda tertarik membeli produk makeup yang diulas karena penggunaan bahasa Inggris? – Are you interested in buying the makeup product because of the English codes used?</i></p> <p>a. <i>Ya</i> (Yes) b. <i>Tidak</i> (No)</p>	
11.	<p><i>Siapakah Beauty vlogger Indonesia yang paling anda sukai? – Who is your most favorite Indonesian beauty vloggers?</i></p> <p>a. Tasya Farasya b. Rachel Goddard c. Indira Kalistha d. Ini Vindy</p>	<p>Questions number 11-12 are made to see the most favourite Indonesian beauty vlogger and the juncture which underlies it.</p>
12.	<p><i>Apa alasan Anda menonton Beauty vlogger Indonesia yang Anda sukai? - Why do you like watching your most favorite beauty vlogger’s vlogs?</i></p> <p>a. Bahasa : b. Penampilan/Performance : c. Konten:</p>	

13.	<i>Siapakah Beauty vlogger Indonesia yang Anda tidak sukai?</i> – Which of the following Indonesian beauty vloggers whom you do not like much? a. Tasya Farasya b. Rachel Goddard c. Indira Kalistha d. Ini Vindy	Questions number 13-14 are written to see the fact that among 4 Indonesian beauty vloggers, there is one or two whom the viewers dislike, along with the reason.
14.	<i>Apa alasan Anda tidak menonton Beauty vlogger Indonesia yang Anda tidak sukai?</i> – Why do not you like to watch the vlogs of beauty vlogger whom you dislike? a. Bahasa : b. Penampilan : c. Konten :	
15.	<i>Apa saran Anda untuk membuat vlog yang lebih menarik?</i> – Do you have any suggestion how to create interesting beauty vlogs?	The last question is open question. It is aimed at gaining more positive and precious input from the viewers. Thus, this input may help vloggers to beautify the vlogs.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

English Use in Vlogs

The analysis results that the first group of beauty vloggers operates English words more than 10% of all words produced. The other group employs less than 10%.

Table 2. The Percentages of English Use among Two Groups of Indonesian Beauty Vloggers

Groups	Vloggers	The total words	English codes	Percentage
First Group	Tasya Farasya	4275	508	11,9 %
	Rachel Goddard	2042	353	14,7%
Second Group	Indira Kalistha	2822	169	5,9%
	Ini Vindy	3935	321	8,1%

The table above undeniably proves that the two groups use different number of English codes. The first two vloggers are assorted to be in the same cluster with the frequent use of English codes. The rest are sorted in the block with the seldom use of English codes. Each vlogger’s table comprising detailed words, phrases, and clauses split into some parts of speech, noun, adjective, verb, adverb, interjection, and conjunction can be checked in the following linked sites.

- https://drive.google.com/file/d/1sqE26dnvgYv2PqvZ6QmUo-Lu_ubUEsHI/view?usp=sharing
- https://drive.google.com/file/d/1qVyiUe85BDFtTyVEW00xDe3Qi2EL_Nu4/view?usp=sharing
- https://drive.google.com/file/d/10c39A-cLSQoK_OO6FYZUnxUQn-B1D_mC/view?usp=sharing
- https://drive.google.com/file/d/1MTZo-HjCEGw0n_jIaitaN7g2JXlualM/view?usp=sharing

Furthermore, the following table details the numbers and occurrences of English use covering some parts of speech distributed to 5 columns; noun, adjective, verb, adverb, and others (interjection, conjunction, other clauses).

Table 3. The Recapitulation of Indonesian Beauty Vloggers' English Use

Vloggers	Noun		Adjective		Verb		Adverb		Others	
	amnt	occ.	amnt	occ.	Amnt	occ.	amnt	occ.	amnt	occ.
TF. 1	37	106	27	49	14	27	1	1	6	6
TF. 2	25	84	18	18	15	33	1	1	6	8
	62	190	45	67	29	60	2	2	12	14
RG. 1	37	98	24	30	18	25	3	3	10	12
RG. 2	17	27	5	5	7	11	2	2	5	5
	54	125	29	35	25	36	5	5	15	17
IK.1	24	56	9	20	11	20	2	3	6	7
IK. 2	14	40	3	6	7	22	2	2	7	7
	38	96	12	26	18	42	4	5	13	14
IV. 1	25	71	13	20	13	18	1	1	3	5
IV. 2	30	75	17	25	8	19	2	4	2	5
	55	146	30	45	21	37	3	5	5	10

Note:

TF. 1= Tasya Farasya , vlog 1

TF. 2 = Tasya Farasya, vlog 2

RG. 1 = Rachel Goddard, vlog 1

RG. 2 = Rachel Goddard, vlog 2

amnt. = the amount of words, phrases, and clauses

occ. = the number of occurrence

IK. 1 = Indira Kalistha, vlog 1

IK. 2 = Indira Kalistha, vlog 2

IV. 1 = Ini Vindy, vlog 1

IV. 2 = Ini Vindy, vlog 2

All four Indonesian beauty vloggers similarly use English nouns referring to *the kinds of product*, such as **lipstick, cushion, foundation, concealer, sponge, primer, highlighter, moisturizer, eyeliner, eye shadow, and toner**. Further, in term of explicating the kinds of product, some adjectives can be revealed in both groups, to wit, **beige, matte, shiny, creamy, and buttery**. In term of applying the product, the particular verbs discovered in all vlogs are **blend** and **swatch**. The other operational words showing activities and directing viewers to react are = **review, share, like, follow, comment, and subscribe**. Additionally, addressing term commonly used is **guys** with various construction, such as **Hi guys** and **OK guys**. The most frequent use of English code for farewell is **bye**. All in all, some English codes are both used by them.

On the contrary, the first group classified as the frequently used-English operates some English codes which could not be found in the second group, such as **ceramide, niacinamide, organic oil, black seed oil, viraid vitamin C, phyto SLC, tea tree, and witch hazel** referring to *the ingredients*. Some adjectives, **oxy, bronzy, peachy, pigmented, velvet, satin, long lasting, and anti-aging**, are the expounding words toward the product that are also merely employed by the first group. Some verbs that are produced by only the first group are **exfoliate, hydrate, endorse, swirl, highlight, pump, and press** which show how the products are applied. Some other expressions revealed to attract viewers' attention such as **keep on watching, thank you so much, I'll see you on the next video, and stay catchy** are commonly uttered by the first group. The second group produces shorter expression such as **oh my God** and **I'm sorry**. Consequently, slight difference is found toward the numbers of English codes used between the two parties due to the above points.

Table 4. The total numbers of parts of speech used in the selected beauty vlogs

	Nouns	Adjectives	Verbs	Adverbs	Others
First group	116	74	54	7	27
Second group	93	42	39	7	18

The above table shows that the numbers of parts of speech used by the first beauty vloggers are more than the second, except for adverbs. Eventually, the dissimilar numbers may be one of the attractiveness of vlogs. The following discussion will construe the variables (English use and purchase intention) as one suite.

Viewers’ Purchase Intention

As it has been elaborated in the method, 15 questions are structured to identify the influence of Indonesian beauty vloggers’ English use toward viewers’ purchase intention. The ensuing discussion presents the result of each question. The netted viewers are 33 who are in various age levels and coming from various towns.

Graph 1. The age levels of viewers

Graph 2. The domicile of the viewers

The viewers’ age level is between 17 to 23 years old. This age level seems match with the common phenomena that most people in that level of age start to think about their performance including the way how they make up. Further, the viewers’ domiciles are various. Most are coming from Jember where the researchers are now living. These two social factors are not included in the analysis since these two social factors are being the proof that this research is objectively conducted.

Question number 1 is set to know whether the respondents have ever watched the vlogs of four selected Indonesian beauty vloggers, namely Tasya Farasya, Rachel Goddard, Indira Kalistha and Ini Vindy. Among 33 respondents, 20 people watch Tasya

Farasya’s vlogs, 8 people watch Rachel Goddard’s vlogs, 4 people watch Indira Kalistha’s vlogs and 1 person watches Ini Vindy’s vlogs.

Chart 1. The number of viewers who watch four selected Indonesian beauty vloggers

The pie chart above shows that most watched vlogs are belonging to Tasya. This is not surprising because Tasya is on the first of the top ten Indonesian beauty vloggers in terms of the number of subscribers (www.socialblade.com). Additionally, the second desirable vlogger is Rachel Goddard with 8 people (24,2%). Although the number is much different from Tasya, but it is twice as much and eight times more than the other two. The result, correspondingly, implies that the first group of Indonesian beauty vloggers (Tasya and Rachel) is more well-known than the other one (Indira and Vindy).

The next question, question number 2 is set to know the frequency of watching Indonesian beauty vloggers’ vlogs. 31 people chose twice till five times and 2 people chose six times until 10 times.

Chart 2. The frequency of watching the four selected Indonesian beauty vloggers

The chart above shows that most viewers spend 2 until 5 times a week to watch the video. It indicates that viewers spend their time regularly watching vlogs. Less number of viewers seem spend time intensely watching them. This fact implies that viewers recognize enough the four selected Indonesian beauty vloggers.

The following questions, question number 3 up to 7 are used to know the viewers’ purchase intention. Question number 3 is asked to know whether viewers are interested in searching information about the make-up product or not after they have watched the vlogs.

Chart 3. Viewers’ interest to seek the information about the product

Among 33 viewers, 28 are interested in seeking the information after they watched the beauty vlogs. It indicates that the gap between the two is big enough., which means that beauty vlogs are very influential.

Question 4 is employed to know that whether the viewers seek more information about makeup products reviewed by Indonesian beauty vloggers.

Chart 4. Viewers' attempt to find more information about the product

In the question number 4, 25 viewers confess that they try to search more information other than what they have watched on the beauty vloggers' vlogs. This step signals that most viewers have been influenced by the online influencers, which indicates that the desire to buy starts to grow. In this step, the viewers' curiosity begins. Having a lot of references about the product will let the desire or curiosity continue to go to the following step.

Question number 5 is used to know whether the viewers are adapted to the product or not.

Chart 5. The viewers' adaptation toward the desired product

The pie chart 5 displays that 20 people are adapted to the product that they have found more about the information. This step implies that the viewers' purchase intention have started to begin. After being influenced by the vloggers, they search more information to fulfil their curiosity, not only from the vlogs but also from other sources. When they think that the product adapts to theirs, they certainly go to the next step.

Question number 6 is addressed to know whether the viewers want to know the detailed precise presentation or specification.

Chart 6. The viewers' attempt to know the product's specification

The result of question number 6 shows that 25 viewers try to know more about the product's specification including the detailed content or ingredients, the amount of the substances, etc. In this step, the viewers' curiosity has been fulfilled. Further, most viewers agree that having known the product's specification will lead them to the final decision, buy the product or ignore it.

Question number 7 is used to know whether the viewers buy the makeup products reviewed by Indonesian beauty vloggers or not.

Chart 7. The viewers' decision to buy the product

The answer of question number 7 shows that 24 viewers finally want to buy the makeup product while the rest do not. Most viewers are completely under the influence of the beauty vlogs.

In sum, the result of the question number 3 up to 7 about viewer's purchase intention shows that the Indonesian beauty vloggers help them to build interest, desire, and curiosity which then lead them to buy the product. Therefore, the Indonesian beauty vloggers play important role in rising viewers' purchase intention. Additionally, the further investigation is realized in the following questions; whether the English use influences them to buy the product or not.

The next question, question number 8 is designed to know whether the viewers are aware that Indonesian beauty vloggers insert some English words.

Chart 8. The viewers' awareness on the English use

From the chart above, it can be seen that most viewers realize that Indonesian beauty vloggers insert some English words. It is then assumed that the English use may attract viewers' attention. However, to know whether the attractiveness of English influences them to watch or to buy the product will be answered in the ensuing questions.

Question number 9 is written to know whether the viewers are interested in watching Indonesian beauty vloggers' vlogs because of the English codes inserted.

Chart 9. The Influence of English use toward the viewers in watching the vlogs

The result of question number 9 shows that 23 viewers admitted that English use do not make them watch Indonesian beauty vloggers' vlogs while 10 people said the opposite. This answer implies that although most viewers realize that they are aware of English codes used in the vlogs but English is not the point that arouses their willing to watch the vlogs.

Quite similar to the previous question, question number 10 is asked to know whether the viewers are interested in buying the product because of the English words used.

Chart 10. The Influence of English use toward the viewers' purchase intention

The answer of question number 10 is not far different from question number 9 which shows that English does not affect them, either to watch or buy the product. Most viewers have bought the product not because of the English codes that are used by the vloggers. Finally, it can be concluded that viewers' purchase intention is not influenced by the English use.

Question number 11 is made up to know who is the Indonesian beauty vlogger that is liked by the viewers.

Chart 11. The most preferable vloggers

The result shows that among 33 respondents, there are 20 viewers who choose Tasya Farassya, 7 viewers choose Rachel Goddard, 4 viewers choose Indira Kalistha and 2 viewers choose Ini Vindy. It is clearly seen that Tasya Farasya is the most preferable beauty vlogger. This result is in line with the previous discussion that Tasya Farasya has more subscribers than the others.

Related to the previous question, question 12 is set to know the reasons why the viewers choose the most preferable beauty vlogger.

Chart 12. The reasons of choosing the most preferable vlogger

The result shows that there are 2 significant reasons why they like one of chosen beauty vloggers. Among 3 reasons, performance entices more viewers than content and language use. There are 21 viewers choosing performance and the rest choosing content. No one chooses language use as the reason. This fact works accordingly with the previous questions (question number 9 and 10) which result that English use does not make the viewers watch vlogs or buy the product.

Question number 13 is the opposite of question number 11. It is questioned to know who is the Indonesian beauty vlogger that the viewers do not like most.

Chart 13. The least preferable vlogger

The above chart shows that the viewers choose Ini Vindy as the Indonesian beauty vlogger whom they do not like. Among 33 respondents, 18 viewers choose Ini Vindy, 5 viewers choose Indira Kalistha, 6 viewers choose Rachel Goddard and 2 viewers choose Tasya Farassya. This result is in accordance with the number of subscribers noted on the above discussion, in which, Ini Vindy has the lowest number than the other three.

Question number 14 is aimed at digging out the reasons why the viewers do not like one of the chosen Indonesian beauty vloggers.

Chart 14. The reasons of choosing the least preferable vlogger

Most viewers still keep performance as the main reason why they like or dislike the vlogger. They also mention content as the second big reason why they do so. Interestingly, language use in this part plays role. Although it is not significant factor, but there are some viewers who do not like the vloggers' way of using language.

Question number 15 is applied to gain suggestions for Indonesian beauty vloggers to beautify the vlogs.

Question 15. Suggestions from the viewers

The result shows that most of viewers focus on the content. Although in the preceding questions (number 12 and 14), viewers mention that performance is the most influential in creating vlogs, but they give input more on content. As it is named “content creator”, vloggers should pay more attention on their content. Some suggestive inputs are: vary the content (not monotonous), detail the content (the more detail the product, the more interesting the vlog), and beautify the content by inserting some jokes and music. Related to the use of language, some viewers suggest to use simple, polite, and understandable language and do not use overreacting expressions.

CONCLUSION

The analysis results that some English codes are both used in the two groups of vloggers. The similar English codes used are covering kinds of product, the description of the product, the way how to apply the product, and some other expressions including greeting and farewell. Although they use some same English codes, but it is also found that some English words do not appear in the second group due to specifying ingredients, expounding the state of the product, clarifying the use of the product, and addressing viewers with specific utterances. Further, the vloggers are found to be very influential toward the viewers. It is evidenced by the fact that the viewers' purchase intention is influenced by the vlogs posted. Nonetheless, the English codes used by some vloggers do not give persuasive effect to the viewers. Most viewers consider performance and content as the reasons why they like or dislike the beauty vlogs. Further they suggest the vloggers to vary the vlogs to avoid monotonous and update the vlogs. Besides, they also appeal to beauty vloggers to be honest in reviewing the product.

This investigation may need improvement to be able to be generalized, since it only takes 2 vlogs of each Indonesian beauty vlogger. Others may take similar investigation to fill the gap that English use may influence viewers' purchase intention in other types of vlogs.

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